

EFFICIENCY OF USING DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN COST MANAGEMENT STRATEGY IN TEXTILE INDUSTRY ENTERPRISES

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Annotatsiya

With the development of the digital economy, enterprises are increasingly paying attention to the use of information technology to reduce costs and improve economic benefits. However, in practical applications, it is not easy to use information technology to control enterprise costs. It is necessary not only to establish an effective cost control mechanism and management model, but also to combine information technology with enterprise costs and hire specialized personnel for management.

Kalit soʻzlar:

Technological development, cost control system, general cost, big data, economic losses.

In a highly competitive market, the goal of business operations is to make a profit. Cost control is the practice of analyzing a company's production system to ensure that the business will achieve expected profitability. Cost control follows the path of revenue to ensure that even with ups and downs, expenses are always proportional to revenue [1]. The work of controlling a company's costs involves analyzing all expenses, regardless of their amount and categorization. Modern businesses often overlook the importance of managing the costs of a company, which leads to unnecessary economic losses that do not contribute to the long-term development of enterprises.

Thus, how to control enterprise costs in the digital economy has become a question that current enterprise managers should think about.

In the era of rapid technological development, some data processing can be analyzed and optimized by using information technology such as big data, artificial intelligence, cloud computing, etc.

However, most enterprises in the country are unable to control costs on the spot, which directly leads to a large number of economic losses and affects the development of subsequent enterprises.

Let us highlight the main problems of cost control.

1. There is no reliable cost control system. In the process of cost management, enterprises often calculate the cost of each department separately, without forming a general cost management system of the enterprise, which also causes a problem,

consisting in the fact that the overall effect of cost management of the enterprise is low.

There are three reasons why enterprises have not formed a reliable cost control system at this stage. The first aspect is that there are problems in the management of the enterprises themselves, and most enterprises have insufficient supervision.

The second aspect is that budget employees do not bear responsibility.

The third aspect is the positioning of the enterprise's self-awareness. Under market pressure, most enterprises exhibit the phenomenon of blind contracting to one degree or another [2].

Thus, the lack of necessary market research and comparison with competitors leads to the fact that procurement is not paid attention to, which increases the cost of procurement, and all purchased materials are useless materials, which brings serious economic losses to the enterprise.

In some technologies, the introduction of technology from outside and the purchase of related equipment are costs, and the same is true for the circulation area. However, the final total cost of the enterprise often does not take into account the costs of technology and circulation areas. In addition, due to the lack of cost control, general cost control often pays attention only to macro needs and the cost of the product itself, but ignores the value of the cost in the market [3]

In order to improve the quality and efficiency of cost control, enterprises need to constantly improve the cost control system. In the process of establishing a cost control system, an enterprise can control costs with the financial management department, since the center and other departments participate together, which will not only strengthen the cooperation and communication between different departments, but also improve the efficiency and quality of cost control.

In particular, the financial department regularly summarizes and analyzes the cost data of each department, identifies the shortcomings in the cost control of each department in the process of analysis, and promptly reports the shortcomings to each department, thereby strengthening the adjustment of the cost control of each department.

In the context of the digital economy, enterprise cost control has opened up new development opportunities[4-6]. Traditional cost control usually relies on manpower to solve problems. Large amounts of data require time and energy. Nowadays, relying on information technology, the powerful computing power and memory capacity of computers can be used to reduce the impact of manual calculations on cost control and improve the efficiency of cost control. In addition, enterprise managers and internal personnel need to increase their awareness of cost control, realize the importance of cost control, and continuously strengthen training and development.

List of Used Literature

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